

GENERATIVE AI FOR PREDICTIVE CREDIT SCORING AND LENDING DECISIONS INVESTIGATING HOW AI IS REVOLUTIONISING CREDIT RISK ASSESSMENTS AND AUTOMATING LOAN APPROVAL PROCESSES IN BANKING

Archana Todupunuri

Fidelity Information Services, USA

ABSTRACT

GenAI is a process that helps in maintaining credit risk assessment and ability for making accurate decisions in loan approval process. Generative AI impacts on the growth of credit risk assessment and automating loan approval processes in the banking sector. Secondary data collection and qualitative strategy have been addressed for developing financial conditions of banking sector. Accumulation of high quality of information can develop outcomes of banking sector to maintain lending decisions and credit risk assessment processes in the banking sector. Data privacy and security can maintain bias in banking sector to develop predictive credit scoring and lending decisions.

Keywords: GenAI, Credit Scoring, Lending Decisions, Banking Sector

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I. INTRODUCTION

Background

Generative AI (GenAI) can create new content such as music, image, video, conversations and text and enhance creativity. GenAI has potential impact in credit risk assessment along with its ability for creating accurate information and understanding predictive approaches. Personal credit risk assessment models can help to develop accuracy of prediction in banking sector for maintaining lending decisions.

Figure 1: Value spending on GenAI in banking sector

From above figure, it can be stated that banking sector focuses on spending on GenAI for developing their customer services. About 6 billion dollars is spent on generative AI in 2024 by banking sector and forecasted to spend about 84.99 billion dollars in 2030 [1]. Use of generative AI in banking sector helps to maintain credit and make it easier for customers to develop risk management. Thus, GenAI is an important part of banking sector to develop organisational performance and reputation.

Rationale

Ineffective management of credit score and lending decisions in banking sector is a major issue in recent times that impacts on growth of financial situation of an organisation. This study is conducted for addressing accurate solutions of credit score management and effective lending decisions in banking sector through generative AI. GenAI can analyse unstructured information from various sources that provides a comprehensive view on financial behaviours and credit risk of applicants [2]. Inadequate credit risk assessment and score management is a major issue as it negatively affects organisational growth and performance. GenAI maintains factual inaccuracies in credit score management in banking sector [3]. Lack of credit risk assessment creates issues in banking sector in recent times as it decreases financial conditions of organisations. Thus, this paper shed light on this issue to maintain credit risk and automotive loan approval process in banking sector.

Aim, research objective and research question

Aim

Main aim of this study is to critically evaluate role of generative AI for revolutionising credit risk assessments and lending decisions in banking sector.

Research objectives

- To evaluate impact of generative AI for predictive credit scoring and lending decisions to maintain credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process
- To analyse benefits of GenAI for predictive credit score and lending decisions in banking sector
- To investigate challenges related to generative AI for predicting credit score and lending decisions to control credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process
- To recommend strategies for mitigating challenges for successful predict credit score and lending decisions in banking

Research questions

RQ1: How does generative AI impact predictive credit score and lending decisions for controlling credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process?

RQ2: What are benefits of GenAI in banking sector for making lending decisions and predicting credit score?

RQ3: What challenges are related to generative AI for predictive credit score and lending decisions for maintaining credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process?

RQ4: What strategies could be incorporated for mitigating challenges and successful predictive credit score and lending decisions?

Scope of the paper

Scope of this paper is to evaluate application of generative AI in banking sector that focuses on dimensions such as predictive credit score and lending decisions. In addition to this, this paper would evaluate reason behind use of generative AI in banking sector that revolutionised credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process. Main scope of this study is to gain knowledge about role of GenAI in revolutionising credit risk assessments and lending decisions in banking sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Impact of generative AI for predictive credit scoring and lending decisions

AI-driven credit scoring systems in banking sector can evaluate a wide range of information and make accurate predictions and decisions about capabilities of borrowing for loans. Financial organisations can obtain understanding about capabilities of borrowers that lead to informed decision-making and a robust financial ecosystem through leveraging generative AI [4]. AI-driven credit scores systems can provide a final credit score for decision makers after evaluating combined information about credit score and loan management capabilities. Besides this, GenAI models focus on neural networks for addressing patterns and structures of existing data for generating new and original content [5]. Following this, use of generative AI has impact on alternative data sources and future potential to develop organisational goals. Use of GenAI has impact on decision making for automotive loan approval process and credit risk assessment in banking sector. Thus, application of generative AI can improve transparency and trustworthiness in banking sector between borrowers and service providers that positively impacts credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process.

Benefits of generative AI for predictive credit score and lending decisions in banking sector

Generative AI enhances predictive risk analysis through evaluating a wide range of datasets and addressing potential risks before materialisation. Generative AI helps to detect fraud through evaluating patterns in customers' information in financial institutions [6]. Use of GenAI benefits various risk factors such as credit risk, market risk and operational risk that provides warning for mitigating issues in banking sector. Integration of generative AI extends personalised information for predictive analytics to develop customer's demands [7]. Generative AI can evaluate financial indicators, market trends and credit histories for providing adequate risk assessment through management of credit risk assessment. Thus, generative AI benefits banking sector to develop credit history and market trends for maintaining financial conditions.

Challenges related to generative AI for predictive credit score and lending decisions

Generative AI faced major challenges like generative realistic and bias in generated content for producing meaningful results. Generative AI is pivotal to generate realistic "virtual content", "personalising experiences", and to creating dynamic virtual globe [8]. GenAI faced a major issue in creating generative realistic and biases in content that negatively impacts automatic loan approval process and credit risk assessment. Generative AI models can capture diversity in datasets that can only generate realistic information [9]. Biases in generated content can negatively impact the credit risk management and lending decisions in banking sector for maintaining an automated loan approval process and credit risk assessment. Therefore, bias can have a negative impact on growth of banking sector in terms of predicting credit score and lending decisions.

Strategies for successful implementation of generative AI in banking sector

Algorithm auditing and transparency for proactively resolving and addressing biases are main strategies for mitigating issues of biases in generated content. Algorithm auditing practices help for monitoring human usage of AI technology that ensures integration of information for avoiding discrepancies [10]. This process evaluates safety, functionality and ethics of AI systems involving GenAI for ensuring legal requirements and best practices. Data security can maintain generative realistic in banking sector for credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process. Generative data needs controllability that can prevent potential threats in banking sector to develop financial conditions [11]. Balance of data security through understanding data flow and implementing access control can improve organisational outcomes that provide adequate services to customers in banking sector. Thus, algorithm auditing, data security and ethical considerations can mitigate challenges of generative AI in banking sector to maintain credit score and lending decisions.

*Theoretical perspective***Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)****Figure 2:** Technology Acceptance Model

(Source: Self-created)

Based on above figure, TAM encompasses components of “perceived usefulness” and “perceived ease of use” that change intention of users to accept a technology. Factors of TAM indirectly impact users that embrace new technology and their attitudes to growth of organisational outcomes [12]. Banking sector can apply this model theory designing training programs and monitoring adoption and usage rates. TAM is about information theory that elucidates ways that encourage the utilisation of technological acceptances in organisations. Application of TAM helps to explain potential behaviours of users for using technologies and innovation that impacts scope of organisation [13]. Application of TAM helps to address factors of innovation and technology that impacts on the credit risk assessment and lending decisions. Thus, implementation of TAM can be effective to develop risk assessment and automotive loan approval processes in banking sector.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section eases procedures for researchers for designing methods that are accurate, dependable to address research questions. Research philosophy, approach, strategy, data collection and analysis process are followed to complete this section and reach research objectives. Research philosophy focuses on brief information requirements to be collected about the given phenomena. “*Interpretivism philosophy*” has been considered in this study for capturing objective information associated with perception of borrowers and lenders. Interpretivism reality is subjective can differ considering various individuals [14]. This philosophy helps to address reality for growth of research outcomes so “*Interpretivism philosophy*” has been selected. Besides this, “*Inductive approach*” has been selected for conducting this study for reaching to research objectives of this study. Researchers gather empirical information for developing concepts based on previous collected information [15]. Empirical evidence was determined in this study for understanding impacts of generative AI in predicting credit score and lending decisions. Thus, “*Interpretivism philosophy*” and “*Inductive approach*” were followed in this study to determine impact of GenAI in banking sectors for automatic loan approval and credit risk assessment.

“*Qualitative strategy*” has been considered for detailed analysis of given research context about generative AI in predictive credit score and lending decisions. “*Qualitative strategy*” helps to address detailed information about a given research context. In addition to this, “*secondary data collection method*” has been selected due to its cost effectiveness to gather relevant information that addresses research objectives. Secondary data is gathered from secondary sources about particular phenomena that help to develop detailed understanding about research context [16].

Secondary data in this study has been gathered from “Google Scholar” to gather relevant information from peer-reviewed journals and articles. Besides this, “*thematic analysis*” has been conducted in this study to draw conclusions through evaluating gathered information in banking sector. Themes were generated from research objectives through address of patterns of datasets. Thus, study incorporated secondary data collection along with thematic analysis to address research questions.

IV. IMPACT AND IMPLICATION

Theme 1: Generative AI helps in making accurate predictions and decisions loan approval

GenAI in lending introduces advanced algorithms for vast amounts of information that involve unconventional sources such as transaction patterns. GenAI has potential for playing a major role for optimising lending operations to achieve future business goals. Generative AI models are recognised for processes for predictive analytics in financial market analysis [17]. Generative AI enables precise credit risk assessments, improves total lending decisions and reduces likelihood of defaults. GenAI defines a class of AI algorithms that can generate new information samples from learned distribution of training datasets [18]. AI can predict likelihood for default through assessing risk factors that allows lenders for making more informed decisions. GenAI has potential for revolutionary ways to make credit decisions by lenders to develop credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval process. Generative AI changes financial institutions for risk management to enhance outcomes of organisations to make effective decisions in growth of financial conditions of business. Therefore, implementation of GenAI helps for accurate predictions and decisions about bowling capabilities for loan approval.

Theme 2: Generative AI provides benefits in developing credit scoring and risk management accurately

Generative AI can develop accuracy of credit scores, improve credit access and reduce financial risks for borrowers. Automation eliminates needs of manual labour that lead to significant cost savings for financial institutions. Deep generative models help to generate latent presentations of input modalities and reconstruct organisational performance [19]. Utilisation of AI algorithms enhances accuracy of credit scoring for developing outcomes for business. Generative AI benefits to develop credit scores and risk management in reaching to future goals of business that make competitive advantage for financial management. Algorithms can introduce bias and reinforce historical discrimination that impacts on credit risk assessment and automotive loan approval [20]. Generative AI plays a crucial role for automating generation of disputes to maintain changes in credit reports. Integrating generative AI in credit risk assessment provides various advantages in banking sector that impacts accuracy and efficiency. Thus, GenAI helps to create sophisticated tools for developing credit scores and risk management in financial conditions.

Theme 3: Biased in generative content of credit create challenge for banking sector in lending decisions and predictive credit score

Generative AI models can inherit biases from information and decrease challenges in banking sector for managing lending decisions and predictive credit score. Ensuring fairness in AI models challenges that need continuous improvement and monitoring for reaching future goals of business. Fairness in credit score impacts bias to customers and enhancing transparency of decision-making process in financial institutions [21].

Generative AI can address suspicious patterns and flag potential fraud attempts through a wide range of transaction information and customer behaviours. Application of generative AI helps to develop credit risk assessment in banking sector to develop financial conditions of organisation [22]. AI systems negatively impact limitation of information in accessing essential services in banking sector for automotive generative AI and credit risk assessment. Therefore, GenAI enables risk assessment in credit score management and lending decisions in financial management.

Theme 4: Algorithm auditing helps to avoid biases in credit risk assessment and lending decisions

Algorithm auditing in banking sector helps to avoid biases in credit risk assessment and develop lending decisions. Accuracy and speed of credit can be developed with the use of AI that allows lenders for making faster and informed decisions on borrowing money. Algorithm auditing is capable of assessing creditworthiness for customers who need short-term loans for specific purposes [23]. Algorithms affect biases on actions and decisions that help to make accurate decisions to achieve future goals. Algorithm auditing bias occurs for creating decisions about unfair outcomes that impact on economic opportunities of organisations in the banking sector. Algorithm bias can lead to misinformed decisions and negative consequences for individuals and organisations that negatively impacts organisational growth [24]. Algorithm auditing manifests individuals along with information being used in algorithms in a designed way to maintain automatic loan approval process and credit risk assessment. Therefore, algorithm auditing can be helpful to achieve future goals of banking sector through management of bias in credit risk assessment and lending decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

From above discussion, it can be concluded that integration of generative AI in banking sector helps to maintain lending decisions and predictive credit scores. Instance of control the previous pattern of lending and credit risk assessment, essential data can be fetched through professionals in banking sector during loan approval. Integration of AI has helped banking professionals for gaining suitable insights of customers for loan approval and credit score management. Generative AI drives a wide range of information and makes accurate predictions about borrowing capabilities of individuals. Use of GenAI in the banking sector can provide a final credit score for decision makers after evaluating combined information about credit score and loan management. GenAI models use neural networks for addressing structures and patterns in existing information for generating new and original context. Bias in generated content is a main challenge of generative AI in the banking sector that can be mitigated through use of algorithm auditing. Thus, generative AI holds a crucial role for revolutionising credit risk assessments and automotive loans approval processes in banking sector.

VI. FUTURE DIRECTION

Future research could emphasise particular dimensions of generative AI such as predictive credit score and lending decisions in banking sector. Future research could be conducted upon influencing predictive credit score and automotive loan approval process. Furthermore, future researchers can focus on personalised treatment strategies in loan approval process through leveraging generative AI to minimise effects of credit risk on banking sector in future. The importance of generative AI in banking sector for maintaining financial conditions and organisational performance could be conducted in future to obtain detailed knowledge about credit score and lending decisions.

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